

1 **Supplementary Information**

2 **Large area gridded population mapping based on building density, height and type from Earth**

3 **Observation data using census disaggregation and bottom-up estimates**

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12 **1. Building density mapping**

13 **a. Imperviousness mapping**

14 A workflow of mapping nation-wide sub-pixel shares of multiple land cover types was established and
15 validated in [1]. This workflow used a machine learning regression-based spectral unmixing approach
16 with artificially mixed training data as described in detail in 2). We here expanded on this workflow
17 with an adapted STM feature set using the 1st, 2nd and 3rd quartile of S2 reflectance, as well as mean
18 and standard deviation of Tasseled Cap Greenness and mean S1 VH-polarized backscatter data from
19 all image acquisitions, as this feature set proved to be more robust for separating impervious surfaces
20 from seasonal soil [3]. At 270 training sites for impervious surfaces across the study area, we retrieved
21 spectral-temporal metrics (STM), i.e. pixel-based time series statistics of reflectance or backscatter
22 [4,5]. Those were then used in the regression to quantify impervious surfaces. Validation using Google
23 Earth © imagery led to an RSME of 19%, MAE of 13%, R^2 of 0.74 and model slope of 0.75.

24 **b. OpenStreetMap for building density**

25 OSM polylines of 39 *highway* classes, 12 *railway* classes as well as polygons of *runways*, *aprons*,
26 *taxiways* and *parking lots* across the study area were extracted from 6). Highway and railway data
27 were buffered with lane and rail widths based on expert-guided estimates. Polygon and buffered
28 polyline data were rasterized, i.e. for each 100 m² grid cell, the area share [%] covered with
29 infrastructure was computed.

30 The workflow of OSM data handling including literature-based assumptions is described in detail in
31 Haberl et al. (in review). As smaller infrastructure such as paved yards or private parking lots are often
32 not included in OSM, we applied a correction factor of 0.57 to the remaining building density. This
33 factor was empirically derived based on a linear regression between generated building density
34 information with rasterized cadastre building footprints of three NUTS-1 units - the city of Berlin and
35 the states of Thuringia and North Rhine-Westphalia (Fig. SI 1.1). As R^2 is increasing with decreasing
36 resolution, we chose to derive the factor at 1000 m resolution. Note that this factor varies regionally,
37 but its variation is rather low across the sites, which suggests a stable correlation. During processing,
38 building density at 10 m spatial resolution was multiplied with this factor. To minimise commission

39 error, we further excluded grid cells with a building density lower than 25 percent, which
40 approximately coincides with the uncertainty (RMSE) of the impervious fraction mapping.

41

42 **Figure SI 1.1** Predicted building fractions after subtraction of rasterized OSM infrastructure data from the impervious
43 fraction map related to reference building fractions from rasterized cadastre data at different spatial resolutions. A
44 correction factor was derived based on the systematic linear overestimation of predicted building fractions.

45 The use of rasterized OSM data for the distinction of buildings and non-building impervious surfaces
46 brings along three challenges: 1) OSM data is rarely providing time stamps, introducing uncertainties
47 through a temporal gap between the data download in 2020 and the target year 2018. 2) OSM does not
48 guarantee feature completeness, as data is crowd-sourced. 3) Literature-derived national road widths
49 might not have been suitable to buffer each OSM line feature. We assume the impact of these issues to
50 be minor, as 1) road network length within the study area was largely stable from 2000 to 2019 [7] and

51 2) an empirical correction factor was introduced to account for impervious surfaces not covered by
52 OSM data.

53 2. Building type mapping

54 We re-utilized all available analysis-ready S1 observations of 2017 and all S2 observations of 2018
55 with a cloud-coverage < 70% across the study area as described in 8). We generated STMs from all
56 observations. Then, S1 and S2 STMs were used to derive 48 SSTMs using opening and closing
57 operators of the median (Q50) and the inter-quartile range (IQR) of eight S2 reflectance bands, three
58 spectral indices as well as median (Q50) S1 VH-polarized backscatter based on a circular kernel of 50
59 m radius (Table SI 2.1). Q50 and IQR have been chosen as an input to SSTM creation in order to
60 cover both average surface conditions and variation throughout the year. Processing was done using
61 the Framework for Operational Radiometric Correction for Environmental monitoring (FORCE, 9).

62 SSTMs in general have been successfully used to classify settlement types due to their ability of
63 characterizing spatial context, for example in mapping Local Climate Zones [10]. A radius of 50 m
64 implies that the building type can be identified based on spectral information of its immediate
65 surroundings and is at the lower end of neighbourhood sizes commonly used to map broader
66 neighbourhood characteristics [11,12].

67 **Table SI 2.1** S1 and S2 features used to derive Opening and Closing SSTMs. NDVI = Normalized Difference Vegetation
68 Index [13], NDBI = Normalized Difference Built-up Index [14], MNDWI = Modified Normalized Difference Water Index
69 [15]. NIR = Near Infrared, SWIR = Short-wave Infrared.

Features for Opening and Closing metrics
S1 VH polarized median & IQR (4 metrics)
S2 reflectance blue median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance green median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance red median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance red edge 1 median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance NIR median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance broad NIR median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance SWIR1 median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance SWIR2 median & IQR (4)

S2 reflectance NDVI median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance NDBI median & IQR (4)
S2 reflectance MNDWI median & IQR (4)

70 We employed a two-step stratified sampling approach. First, we collected one sample per class and per
71 district (NUTS-3), resulting in 1,604 regionally balanced training samples. Sites were selected based
72 on a visual interpretation of the building density map and VHR imagery from Google Earth ©.
73 Training sites were collected in cells where only one building type was apparent. If possible, the cell
74 had to be at least partly covered by a building, i.e. building density > 25%. We extracted SSTMs at the
75 training sites with the respective class label. An RF classification was performed, using a random
76 subset of 70% of all samples for training and 30% of the data for validation. We used an ensemble of
77 500 trees with the square root of the number of all features randomly selected in each tree [16].

78 After obtaining first results, we performed a second sampling. This was used to compensate for large
79 NUTS-3 units with a high population and high within-class diversity that were under-represented by
80 the equal-number sampling. We additionally selected up to 40 sample sites per NUTS-1 unit, resulting
81 in a new total of 2,149 sites. The selection of new sites was based on RF class probabilities and RF
82 class margins of the first mapping iteration. We concentrated the effort of re-sampling to areas subject
83 to high model uncertainty with an RF class probability of the winning class < 60% and an RF margin,
84 i.e. the class probability distance from the winning to the second class, < 20%. The RF procedure was
85 repeated with the same parameterization using the increased training data.

86 In order to assess building type classification quality, we established a confusion matrix including
87 overall classification accuracy as well as class-wise user's and producer's accuracy [17]. We
88 additionally compared residential building type classification results to residential building type
89 distributions from census data on a NUTS-1 level [18]. Producer's accuracy ranged between 71.29
90 percent for MF and 90.23 percent for SF buildings. User's accuracy ranged between 77.42 percent for
91 MF and 96.55 percent for LS buildings (Table SI 2.2).

92 **Table SI 2.2** Confusion matrix and respective RF class accuracy based on a 30% sub-sample of all class samples, including
 93 user's and producer's accuracy, overall accuracy (OA)

		Reference				n	User's Acc.
		IC	SF	LS	MF		
Pred	IC	159	4	2	16	181	87.84 %
	SF	10	194	3	42	249	77.91 %
	LS	0	1	28	0	29	96.55 %
	MF	26	16	0	144	186	77.42 %
		n	195	215	33	202	
		Prod. Acc.	81.54 %	90.23 %	84.48 %	71.29 %	OA = 81.40 %

94 Across the study area, about 24 percent of all classified cells were categorized as IC, 62 percent as SF,
 95 2 percent as LS and 12 percent as MF. While shares of LS buildings were relatively stable across the
 96 federal states, the share of IC buildings ranges from 16.02 percent in Berlin to 33.94 percent in
 97 Bremen. The share of MF is highest in the three city states (up to 43.14 percent in Berlin) and lowest
 98 in states with a low built-up density (minimum 6.93 percent in Brandenburg). SF housing ranges from
 99 35.48 percent in the city of Hamburg to 72.16 percent in Saarland. Across all 13 areal federal states
 100 (NUTS-1), the ratio of SF to MF residential buildings was over- or underestimated by an average of
 101 2.0 percentage points compared to 2011 census data. In the three city states (Berlin, Hamburg,
 102 Bremen), the share of MF residential buildings was overestimated by 8.85 percentage points on
 103 average. Overall, the R^2 achieved for the building type classification is 0.93 for SF and 0.86 for MF
 104 buildings (Figure 2.1).

105

106 **Figure 2.1:** **Left:** Predicted share of single-family and multi-family built-up cells in all 16 NUTS-1 units compared to census
107 references. **Right:** Relative distribution of all predicted building types (left bar) and reference residential buildings (right bar)
108 for all 16 NUTS-1 units. State abbreviations provided in SI 3.

109 We mapped the type of a building suggested by its structure, as the actual building function is
110 impossible to detect from satellite imagery (e.g. an abandoned production site now used for residential
111 purposes). With regard to RQ1, our ability to distinguish residential (SF and MF) and non-residential
112 (IC and LS) buildings was specifically helpful to exclude unpopulated areas. Comparing SF and MF
113 building shares to reference data at NUTS-1 level showed that those structures were also well covered,
114 except for a slight underestimation of SF housing in city states where the density of SF buildings is
115 higher and more similar to MF structures than in small towns. The sampling of SF and MF housing
116 was sometimes challenging when SF and MF buildings resembled, also complicated by the fact that
117 SF buildings subsumed single- and two-family houses in order to be consistent with census data. In
118 city centers, mixed use was a possible source of error and was mostly sampled as MF housing, as
119 commercial activity usually occupies the ground floor only. Here, confusion could appear with regard
120 to office buildings. Potential effects of the temporal gap between S1 (2017) and S2 (2018) imagery are
121 minor, as building stocks in Germany grew by only 6‰ in 2018 [19].

122 **3. Opening and closing**

123 Opening and closing are morphological operators based on both, in our case grayscale, erosion and
124 dilation [20]. Opening is an erosion followed by a dilation. It is, thus, a selection of the minimum
125 value of all pixels within the radius followed by a selection of the maximum value of those minima
126 within the radius. Opening reduces the occurrence and size of patches with comparatively high
127 reflectance. Closing is a dilation followed by an erosion. It is the selection of the minimum of all
128 maxima within the SE and reduces the occurrence and size of patches with comparatively low
129 reflectance.

130 **4. Federal state abbreviations (NUTS-1 units)**

131 **Table SI 4** Abbreviations for German Federal States (corresponds to NUTS-1 units)

Abbreviation	Federal State
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BW	Baden-Württemberg
BY	Bavaria
BE	Berlin
BB	Brandenburg
HB	Bremen
HH	Hamburg
HE	Hesse
MV	Mecklenburg-Vorpommern
NI	Lower Saxony
NW	North Rhine-Westphalia
RP	Rhineland-Palatinate
SL	Saarland
SN	Saxony
ST	Saxony-Anhalt
SH	Schleswig-Holstein
TH	Thuringia

132

133 **5. Living floor area per capita**

134 The presented bottom-up modeling approach relied on information on living floor area per capita
135 (LFA/cap) in both single-family (SF) and multi-family (MF) buildings. BU-LFA used regionalized
136 data, i.e. that an individual LFA/cap for SF and MF was used for each federal state (Table SI 5.1). We
137 derived $LFA/cap_{t,s}$ as the ratio of the total living floor area of all units of a building type and the people
138 living in a all buildings of that type, with t being the building type and s being the state (eq. SI 5.1).
139 Spatial sensitivity analysis, i.e. the use of spatially incomplete LFA/cap information is conducted with
140 data from each of the federal states. State-level census data is provided for the year 2011 [21].

141 (eq SI 5.1)
$$LFA/cap_{t,s} = \frac{LFA/unit_{t,s} * Units_s * ShareOfUnits_{t,s}}{Population_s * ShareOfUnits_t}$$

142 **Table SI 5.1** Living floor area per capita (LFA/cap) for single-family (SF) and multi-family (MF) buildings in all NUTS-1
 143 units (Federal States) and census information used in eq. SI 5.1.

State	Population	Units		LFA/unit (m ²)		LFA/cap (m ²)	
		SF	MF	SF	MF	SF	MF
BW	11,023,425	2,380,413	2,438,236	116.7	74.8	51.0	32.7
BY	12,997,204	2,986,676	2,790,260	121.6	70.4	54.0	31.3
BE	3,613,495	189,026	1,646,180	115.4	67.3	58.6	34.2
BB	2,504,040	600,654	632,722	106.9	61.6	52.7	30.3
HB	681,032	116,619	219,460	111.3	63.6	54.9	31.4
HH	1,830,584	180,661	709,296	113.8	65.2	55.3	31.7
HE	6,243,262	1,398,378	1,409,609	119.6	72.4	53.8	32.6
MV	1,611,119	338,873	499,922	107.5	59.5	56.0	31.0
NI	7,962,775	2,207,784	1,490,347	122.1	71.0	56.7	33.0
NW	17,912,134	3,549,012	4,901,017	116.8	69.8	55.1	33.0
RP	4,073,679	1,166,425	733,289	122.3	74.2	57.0	34.6
SL	994,187	332,411	154,281	117.5	73.1	57.5	35.8
SN	4,081,308	953,395	1,284,622	98.7	62.8	54.1	34.4
ST	2,223,081	534,395	720,054	102.5	61.7	57.8	34.8
SH	2,889,821	742,676	597,895	115.4	65.4	53.5	30.3
TH	2,151,205	517,523	600,238	102.2	62.8	53.1	32.6

144

145 Temporal sensitivity analysis, i.e. the use of temporally outdated LFA/cap information with Earth
 146 Observation-based products from 2018, is based on historic census data [19]. Historic census data does
 147 not include NUTS-1-level information and is available on a national level including West and East
 148 Germany from 1994 on. This dataset is not entirely consistent with the 2011 census data. We derive
 149 LFA/unit for a building type using the ratio of the total area of all units and the total number of units
 150 of a type. We divide that by the average number of people living in one unit, using the ratio of the total

151 population in that year and the total number of units, assuming that the household size in SF and MF
 152 units is comparable (eq. SI 5.2).

153 (eq. SI 5.2) $LFA/cap_{t,a} = \frac{\frac{AreaOfUnits_t}{Units_t}}{\frac{Population}{Units}}$

154 **Table SI 5.2** Living floor area per capita (LFA/cap) for single-family (SF) and multi-family (MF) buildings from 1994 to
 155 2018 and census information used in eq. SI 5.2. Spatial Scale: NUTS-0.

Year	Population	Units		Total Area (1/1000 m ²)		LFA/cap (m ²)	
		SF	MF	SF	MF	SF	MF
1994	81,338,000	15,897,356	18,802,886	1,660,357	1,233,200	44.6	28.0
1995	81,539,000	16,107,724	19,158,899	1,686,809	1,258,004	45.3	28.4
1996	81,817,000	16,300,230	19,499,930	1,711,276	1,281,218	45.9	28.7
1997	82,012,000	16,516,525	19,814,323	1,738,984	1,304,221	46.6	29.2
1998	82,057,000	16,741,748	20,054,858	1,768,179	1,321,629	47.3	29.5
1999	82,037,000	16,986,070	20,254,220	1,799,911	1,336,752	48.1	30.0
2000	82,163,000	17,219,958	20,409,568	1,830,796	1,348,941	48.7	30.3
2001	82,260,000	17,408,619	20,512,534	1,856,204	1,357,772	49.2	30.5
2002	82,440,000	17,585,111	20,572,800	1,879,730	1,363,939	49.5	30.7
2003	82,537,000	17,754,042	20,615,923	1,903,340	1,368,628	49.8	30.8
2004	82,532,000	17,933,798	20,652,745	1,928,085	1,373,193	50.3	31.1
2005	82,501,000	18,087,964	20,684,473	1,949,557	1,377,292	50.7	31.3
2006	82,438,000	18,240,238	20,731,024	1,970,914	1,382,203	51.1	31.5
2007	82,315,000	18,365,864	20,766,359	1,988,835	1,386,335	51.4	31.7
2008	82,218,000	18,461,934	20,805,953	2,002,844	1,390,556	51.8	31.9
2009	82,002,000	18,545,943	20,844,525	2,015,181	1,394,638	52.2	32.1
2010	81,802,000	18,162,046	20,542,952	2,121,200	1,418,431	55.3	32.7
2011	81,752,000	18,252,882	20,596,184	2,134,694	1,423,436	55.6	32.8

2012	80,328,000	18,351,090	20,665,140	2,149,361	1,429,779	56.9	33.6
2013	80,524,000	18,452,231	20,743,263	2,164,467	1,436,835	57.1	33.7
2014	80,767,000	18,557,401	20,850,325	2,180,232	1,446,271	57.3	33.8
2015	81,198,000	18,658,494	20,961,863	2,195,537	1,456,026	57.4	33.9
2016	82,176,000	18,762,486	21,086,208	2,211,256	1,466,627	57.2	33.7
2017	82,522,000	18,866,038	21,222,311	2,226,956	1,478,065	57.3	33.8
2018	82,792,000	18,966,444	21,369,968	2,242,305	1,490,084	57.6	34.0

156

157 **6. Adjusted building volume**

158 Using building volume as a covariate for gridded population does not account for the fact that
159 population density can be higher in multi-family dwellings than in single-family dwellings. Census
160 data confirms that living floor area per capita is different in buildings of those categories (refer to main
161 text), and different assumptions on this are accounted for in the bottom-up population mapping
162 approach. In our top-down approach, we employed a sensitivity analysis and tested a variety of
163 weighting factors to increase building volume of multi-family buildings and, thus, the population that
164 is redistributed to that building type. Even though different weighing factors for multi-family buildings
165 perform best at some scales and regarding some quality metrics, it turned out that a volume weighting
166 factor of 1.6 yields best results with regard to most quality metrics at NUTS-3- and LAU-level. WD-
167 VOLADJ1.6 is, thus, the model which was used for the comparison to other models in the main study.

168 **Table SI 6** Prediction quality of models using different volume weighting factors for multi-family buildings.

<i>Slope</i>	WD-VOLADJ	WD-VOLADJ	WD-VOLADJ	WD-VOLADJ	WD-VOLADJ
<i>R²</i>	1.2	1.4	1.6	1.8	2.0
<i>RMSE</i>					
<i>MAE</i>					
<i>MAPE</i>					
NUTS-1	1.05	1.05	1.04	1.04	1.04
	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.98	0.97
	736,973	756,830	792,105	829,127	870,508
	559,229	553,387	571,689	586,728	601,994
	14.55	13.43	13.32	13.19	13.13
NUTS-3	0.93	0.98	1.02	1.06	1.09
	0.96	0.97	0.97	0.97	0.97
	49,967	46,204	46,624	49,788	54,651

	33,300 19.05	32,208 18.37	32,527 18.04	33,159 17.93	34,074 18.05
LAU	0.93 0.99 6,309 1,408 35.91	0.98 0.99 5,556 1,381 34.45	1.03 0.99 5,855 1,411 33.65	1.07 0.99 6,795 1,454 33.27	1.10 0.99 8,025 1,503 33.22
BPA	0.72 0.65 3,574 2,646 65.66	0.79 0.64 3,582 2,617 68.43	0.84 0.63 3,701 2,678 71.7	0.89 0.62 3,887 2,813 75.21	0.93 0.62 4,080 2,968 78.03

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170 **7. Validation units and census population within REE ranges**

171 **Table SI 7.1** Number of LAU units within ranges of REE using different gridded population models

REE value range	BD-BUILD	BD-RESI	WD-DENS	WD-VOL	WD-VOLADJ	BU-LFA
[-100,-50]	154	62	124	369	621	1004
] -50,-25]	989	543	728	1382	2111	2617
] -25,-10]	1249	846	998	1603	1882	2006
] -10,0]	1031	830	930	1184	1294	1333
]0,10]	1112	985	1014	1230	1177	990
]10,25]	1509	1562	1624	1661	1378	1180
]25,50]	1832	2409	2239	1794	1364	980
]50,100]	1876	2578	2315	1293	834	639
]100	1288	1237	1080	537	392	304

172

173 **Table SI 7.2** Census population within ranges of REE using different gridded population models

REE value range	BD-BUILD	BD-RESI	WD-DENS	WD-VOL	WD-VOLADJ	BU-LFA
[-100,-50]	6,374,781	2,100,092	736,611	601,406	1,068,888	1,756,495
] -50,-25]	19,578,069	23,408,807	23,353,404	11,207,126	10,261,850	11,495,934
] -25,-10]	13,967,519	12,176,832	13,171,745	20,839,755	16,737,379	14,015,843
] -10,0]	8,306,254	7,909,988	8,793,907	15,077,135	13,210,232	15,569,279
]0,10]	7,552,312	8,402,756	7,981,757	10,894,456	17,408,468	12,965,058

[10,25]	9,333,850	9,769,651	10,853,181	12,015,896	14,358,032	17,039,464
[25,50]	9,088,909	10,725,295	10,292,866	8,540,016	7,171,353	7,880,920
[50,100]	6,082,293	6,877,418	6,449,702	3,276,165	2,318,404	1,850,071
[100]	2,505,389	1,421,395	1,159,061	340,348	257,697	219,239

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175 **8. Gridded population results**

176

177 **Figure SI 8:** Population redistribution accuracies at different spatial validation scales (NUTS-1 to LAU and BPA) using the
 178 different approaches (BD-BUILD to WD-VOLADJ). Axes have logarithmic scale. Top-down binary models using building
 179 presence (BD-BUILD), type (BD-RESI). Weighted models using building density (BD-DENS), volume (BD-VOL) and
 180 adjusted volume (BD-VOLADJ). Bottom-up model using living floor area per capita (BU-LFA).

181

182 **References**

183 1. Schug F, Frantz D, Okujeni A, van der Linden S, Hostert P. Mapping urban-rural gradients of
 184 settlements and vegetation at national scale using Sentinel-2 spectral-temporal metrics and
 185 regression-based unmixing with synthetic training data. Remote Sensing of Environment. 2020;
 186 246:111810. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2020.111810.

- 187 2. Okujeni A, van der Linden S, Suess S, Hostert P. Ensemble Learning From Synthetically Mixed
188 Training Data for Quantifying Urban Land Cover With Support Vector Regression. *IEEE J Sel Top*
189 *Appl Earth Observations Remote Sensing*. 2017; 10:1640–50.
190 doi: 10.1109/JSTARS.2016.2634859.
- 191 3. Schug F, Frantz D, Okujeni A, van der Linden S, Hostert P. Land cover fraction map of Germany
192 at 10m spatial resolution based on Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 spectral temporal metrics.
193 PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science; 2020.
- 194 4. Müller H, Rufin P, Griffiths P, Barros Siqueira AJ, Hostert P. Mining dense Landsat time series for
195 separating cropland and pasture in a heterogeneous Brazilian savanna landscape. *Remote*
196 *Sensing of Environment*. 2015; 156:490–9. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.10.014.
- 197 5. Potapov PV, Turubanova SA, Tyukavina A, Krylov AM, McCarty JL, Radeloff VC, et al. Eastern
198 Europe's forest cover dynamics from 1985 to 2012 quantified from the full Landsat archive.
199 *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 2015; 159:28–43. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.11.027.
- 200 6. Geofabrik Download Server. Geofabrik 2020 [cited 30 Jan 2020]. Available from:
201 <https://download.geofabrik.de>.
- 202 7. Federal Stat. Office, editor. Gesamtlänge der Straßen des überörtlichen Verkehrs in
203 Deutschland von 1995 bis 2019 (in 1.000 Kilometer) [Graph]. 2019 [cited 14 Sep 2020].
204 Available from: [https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/2990/umfrage/gesamtlaenge-](https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/2990/umfrage/gesamtlaenge-der-strassen-des-ueberoertlichen-verkehrs/)
205 [der-strassen-des-ueberoertlichen-verkehrs/](https://de.statista.com/statistik/daten/studie/2990/umfrage/gesamtlaenge-der-strassen-des-ueberoertlichen-verkehrs/).
- 206 8. Frantz D, Schug F, Okujeni A, Navacchi C, Wagner W, van der Linden S, et al. National-scale
207 mapping of building height using Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 time series. *Remote Sensing of*
208 *Environment*. 2021; 252:112128. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2020.112128.
- 209 9. Frantz D. FORCE—Landsat + Sentinel-2 Analysis Ready Data and Beyond. *Remote Sensing*. 2019;
210 11:1124. doi: 10.3390/rs11091124.
- 211 10. Verdonck M-L, Okujeni A, van der Linden S, Demuzere M, Wulf R de, van Coillie F. Influence of
212 neighbourhood information on ‘Local Climate Zone’ mapping in heterogeneous cities.
213 *International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geoinformation*. 2017; 62:102–13.
214 doi: 10.1016/j.jag.2017.05.017.
- 215 11. Bechtel B, Alexander P, Böhner J, Ching J, Conrad O, Feddema J, et al. Mapping Local Climate
216 Zones for a Worldwide Database of the Form and Function of Cities. *IJGI*. 2015; 4:199–219.
217 doi: 10.3390/ijgi4010199.
- 218 12. Rosentreter J, Hagensieker R, Waske B. Towards large-scale mapping of local climate zones
219 using multitemporal Sentinel 2 data and convolutional neural networks. *Remote Sensing of*
220 *Environment*. 2020; 237:111472. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2019.111472.
- 221 13. Tucker CJ. Red and photographic infrared linear combinations for monitoring vegetation.
222 *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 1979; 8:127–50. doi: 10.1016/0034-4257(79)90013-0.
- 223 14. Zha Y, Gao J, Ni S. Use of normalized difference built-up index in automatically mapping urban
224 areas from TM imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*. 2003; 24:583–94.
225 doi: 10.1080/01431160304987.

- 226 15. Xu H. Modification of normalised difference water index (NDWI) to enhance open water
227 features in remotely sensed imagery. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*. 2006; 27:3025–
228 33. doi: 10.1080/01431160600589179.
- 229 16. Breiman L. Random Forests. *Machine Learning*. 2001; 45:5–32. doi: 10.1023/A:1010933404324.
- 230 17. Olofsson P, Foody GM, Herold M, Stehman SV, Woodcock CE, Wulder MA. Good practices for
231 estimating area and assessing accuracy of land change. *Remote Sensing of Environment*. 2014;
232 148:42–57. doi: 10.1016/j.rse.2014.02.015.
- 233 18. Census db. from Fed. Stat. Offices, editor. Zensus 2011. Bayerisches Landesamt für Statistik
234 2011 [cited 23 Jun 2020]. Available from: <https://ergebnisse.zensus2011.de/?locale=en#Home>:
- 235 19. Gebäude und Wohnungen. Bestand an Wohnungen und Wohngebäuden, Bauabgang von
236 Wohnungen und Wohngebäuden, Lange Reihen ab 1969 - 2018. ; 2019.
- 237 20. Benediktsson JA, Pesaresi M, Arnason K. Classification and feature extraction for remote
238 sensing images from urban areas based on morphological transformations. *IEEE Trans Geosci
239 Remote Sensing*. 2003; 41:1940–9. doi: 10.1109/tgrs.2003.814625.
- 240 21. Gebäude- und Wohnungsbestand in Deutschland. ; 2014.
- 241